

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL RESEARCH

“FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF GASTRO RETENTIVE IN- SITU FLOATING GELS OF ATORVASTATIN CALCIUM CUBOSOMES”

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ARTICLE INFO

Article history

Received 09/01/2018

Available online

05/02/2018

Keywords

Cubosome,
Floating,
Gastro Retentive,
In-Situ Gel,
Lyotropic Liquid Crystal,
Oraldrugdelivery.

ABSTRACT

Atorvastatin calcium is a BCS class-II competitive HMG-CoA reductase inhibitor having a half-life (almost 14 hour). The aim of the present work is to formulate and evaluate gastro retentive in-situ floating gels of atorvastatin calcium in form of cubosomes. The drug, excipients and formulation are characterized by FTIR. Cubosomes are prepared by Top down approach employing Glyceryl monooleate (GMO) as lipid phase vehicle, Pluronic F127 as stabilizer and distilled water as aqueous phase, Atorvastatin calcium as active pharmaceutical ingredient. The resultant cubosome dispersion is evaluated for drug release by diffusion studies, subjected to zeta-sizing and visualized by transmission electron microscopy. Floating gels are prepared in a manner similar to cubosome dispersion employing gelling agents like Sodium alginate, Guar gum, Xanthan gum, Carbopol 934 B.P. The formulated gels are evaluated for viscosity, gelation property, pH and drug release by diffusion studies. The compatibility studies by infrared spectroscopy showed no interaction between the drug and excipients. Cubosome formulation ACF6 containing 25% GMO showed a maximum drug release of 94 % within 5 hours. The concentration of GMO from above optimized cubosome formulation is used in formulation of floating gels. Sustained release up to 8 hours was observed in gels formulated with carbopol 934, guar gum and Sodium alginate (ACFCNG2). In vitro release kinetics exhibited sustained release and followed non- Fickian diffusion and secondary case 2 by the optimized formulations. Satisfactory viscosity and pH values are obtained.

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Please cite this article in press as **Dr. M. Sunitha Reddy et al.** “Formulation and Evaluation of Gastro Retentive In- Situ Floating Gels of Atorvastatin Calcium Cubosomes”. *Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*.2018;8(01).

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INTRODUCTION

Cubosomes are discrete, sub-micron, nano-organized particles of bicontinuous cubic fluid crystalline stage. Cubosomes have an indistinguishable microstructure from the parent cubic stage however have bigger particular surface territory and their scatterings have much lower consistency in contrast with the mass cubic stage. Lipids, surfactants and polymer particles have both polar and non polar segments, named as amphiphilic. The hydrophobic impact drives amphiphilic particles in polar solvents to immediately self collecting in to a variety of thermodynamically stable fluid crystalline stages with lengths on nanometer scale [2]. A case is the bicontinuous cubic fluid crystalline stage. Bicontinuous cubic stages are optically isotropic, extremely gooey and strong like fluid crystalline substance having cubic crystallographic symmetry.

✓ **ADAVANTAGES OF CUBOSOMES:**

- ✓ Relatively straightforward technique for arrangement.
- ✓ Biodegradability of lipids.
- ✓ Capability of exemplifying hydrophilic, hydrophobic and amphiphilic substances.
- ✓ Targeted discharge and controlled arrival of bioactive operators.
- ✓ They offer an expansive surface region, low consistency and exist at any weakening level.

PREPARATION TECHNIQUES:

Top down Technique [1, 2]:

It is the most broadly utilized strategy. Mass cubic stage is first delivered and by use of high vitality, for example, high weight homogenization it is handled into cubosomes nanoparticles. Mass cubic stage looks like a reasonable unbending gel framed by water-swollen cross-connected polymer chains. The cubic stages vary in that they are a solitary thermodynamic stage and have occasional fluid crystalline structure. Cubic stages cracks toward a path parallel to the shear course, the vitality required is relative to the quantity of tubular system branches that burst

Bottom up technique:

In this cubosomes are permitted to shape or solidify from antecedents. The base up approach initially frames the nanostructure building pieces and afterward collects them into the last material. It is all the more as of late created strategy of cubosome arrangement, enabling cubosomes to frame and take shape from antecedents on the sub-atomic length scale. The key factor of this procedure is hydrotrope that can break up water insoluble lipids into fluid antecedents

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Drug was gifted by hetero labs Atorvastatin calcium and Glycerol mono oleate, Sodium Alginate, Guar Gum, Xanthan Gum, Pluronic F127, Carbopol 934 B.P, are finar chemicals.

Cubosomes Formulations:

Formulation code	Glycerol monooleate		Distilled Water		Stabilizer (in mg) (Polaxomer 407)
	(%v/v)	(in ml)	(%v/v)	(in ml)	
ACF 1	5	0.25	95	4.75	70.5
ACF 2	10	0.5	90	4.5	15
ACF 3	15	0.75	85	4.25	22.5
ACF 4	20	1.00	80	4.00	30
ACF 5	25	1.25	75	3.75	37.5
ACF 6	30	1.50	70	3.50	45
ACF 7	35	1.75	65	3.05	52.5
ACF 8	40	2.00	60	3.00	60
ACF 9	45	2.25	55	2.75	67.5
ACF 10	50	2.50	50	2.50	75

RESULTS & DISCUSSION:

Atorvastatin calcium Standard graph [2, 3]:

Determination of λ_{max} of Atorvastatin calcium in 0.1N HCl:

The spectrum shows maximum absorption at 238nm

Figure 5.1 UV absorption spectrum of Atorvastatin calcium in 0.1N HCl.

Concentration (ppm)	Absorbance
2	0.028
4	0.05
6	0.069
8	0.09
10	0.108

Figure: Atorvastatin calcium Standard graph in 0.1N HCl.

FTIR Studies:

The interaction examines between the medication and excipients and additionally enhanced detailing was assessed utilizing IR spectrophotometer. Atorvastatin calcium has characteristic absorption peaks at 3363.7cm⁻¹, 1585.6cm⁻¹, 1651.4cm⁻¹, 1106.3cm⁻¹, 2969.9cm⁻¹, 3058.4cm⁻¹ and 1063.5cm⁻¹ separately. Comparable peaks were seen in spectra of various combinations of excipients and in improved plan (Cubosomes and gliding gels), alongside nonappearance of interfering peaks showing there is no undesirable response between Atorvastatin calcium and different excipients utilized as a part of the investigation.

Figure: Atorvastatin calcium FT-IR spectrum.

Figure: GMO FT-IR spectrum.

Figure: Sodium alginate FT-IR spectrum.

Figure: Guar gum FT-IR spectrum.

Figure: Xanthan gum FT-IR spectrum.

Figure: FT-IR of Atorvastatin & GMO.

Figure: Overlay of Atorvasatin calcium +GMO.

Figure: FT-IR overlay of Atorvastatin calcium +GMO; GMO.

Figure: FT-IR overlay of Atorvasatin calcium+carbopol 934.

Cubosomes Diffusion Studies:

Time in (hrs)	ACF1	ACF2	ACF3	ACF4	ACF5	ACF6	ACF7	ACF8	ACF9	ACF10
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1	7.8±0.24	9.6±0.17	10.8±0.23	12.9±0.33	15.2±0.21	18.6±0.51	11.3±0.12	12.2±0.55	13.7±0.33	15.3±0.44
2	27.5±0.82	31.5±0.47	37.3±0.39	40.2±0.59	42.1±0.48	38.5±0.27	34.3±0.33	30.7±0.28	28.3±0.46	42.7±0.59
3	43.8±0.23	54.3±0.82	64.2±0.54	66.4±0.28	69.3±0.59	68.7±0.78	58.2±0.87	62.3±0.71	52.9±0.78	56.4±0.76
4	67.1±0.44	73.1±0.47	77.1±0.68	70.7±0.43	83.1±0.97	83.3±0.63	76.4±0.54	68.3±0.34	72.7±0.96	76.1±0.58
5	76.9±0.78	82.7±0.56	88.6±0.33	82.6±0.57	88.7±0.65	94.9±0.45	84.9±0.38	77.9±0.55	84.7±0.48	86.4±0.33

Figure: cumulative drug release % of different formulation.

Droplet size & Zeta potential determination:

From the dissolution study it was concluded that the formulation ACF6 showed more drug release % than other formulation. So it is selected as the best formulation. Size and potential values are determined for the formulation. Size of the particles was found to be 1017nm and pdi value was found to be 0.312 and its zeta potential was found to be -6.1mv.

Figure: distribution of size ACF6 formulation.

Transmission electron microscopy:

At a magnification of up to 1000x, cubosomes are clearly visible. Both placebo and Optimized formulation were observed. Cube like structures along with spherical vesicles are evident both in placebo and optimized formulation not much difference was observed in placebo

A placebo formulation b) optimized formulation gel

Gastro retentive in-situ floating gels:**Diffusion studies:**

Diffusion studies are performed for above combinations and best ones among those are selected based on cumulative drug release values and subjected to other evaluation parameters. The various drug release profiles of formulations and cumulative drug release values of selected gel formulations are give below:

Table: drug release profiles of formulations ACFN1 to ACFX3.

Time in (hours)	ACFN1	ACFN2	ACFN3	ACFX1	ACFX2	ACFX3
0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1	28.5±0.53	27.3±0.27	26.3±0.33	19.4±0.84	21.2±0.22	20.1±0.98
2	29.8±0.62	34.2±0.42	32.9±0.68	25.3±0.73	28.1±0.43	29.2±0.78
3	42.9±0.78	44.3±0.99	43.2±0.87	33.5±0.65	32.9±0.56	33.1±0.46
4	49.3±0.93	51.6±0.87	47.5±0.25	44.2±0.44	45.6±0.79	46.2±0.33
5	53.2±0.21	58.6±0.48	55.2±0.79	50.1±0.75	51.2±0.65	53.1±0.72
6	71.2±0.43	82.1±0.55	72.8±0.21	62.5±0.43	61.5±0.53	64.2±0.19

Figure: Drug release profiles of formulations ACFN1 to ACFX3.**TABLE: drug release profiles of formulations ACFG1 to ACFNGX.**

Time (hrs)	ACFG1	ACFG2	ACFG3	ACFNG1	ACFNG2	ACFNGX
0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1	13.5±0.92	12.8±0.11	13.9±0.44	15.2±0.23	12.9±0.53	11.9±0.13
2	20.99±0.29	29.5±0.55	33.14±0.29	30.2±0.33	27.1±0.72	31.9±0.28
3	41.2±0.73	38.15±0.73	40.5±0.82	39.6±0.94	40.3±0.69	46.5±0.47
4	45.3±0.79	44.5±0.95	43.9±0.19	42.2±0.96	44.3±0.76	57.6±0.35
5	56.8±0.21	55.2±0.49	58.2±0.37	66.5±0.82	60.1±0.35	65.9±0.84
6	71.1±0.94	60.4±0.74	71.11±0.96	82.1±0.38	71.3±0.44	81±0.61

Figure: drug release profiles of formulations ACFG1 to ACFNGX.

Table: Drug release profiles of formulations ACFNX1 to ACFCN2.

Time in (hours)	ACFNX1	ACFNX2	ACFCN1	ACFCN2
0	0	0	0	0
1	27.9±0.23	31.5±0.59	28.2±0.37	29.99±0.19
2	38.11±0.44	44.2±0.65	38.9±0.11	37.3±0.23
3	41.9±0.83	48.3±0.81	42.3±0.58	46.5±0.53
4	53.2±0.75	55.3±0.95	51.3±0.69	50.1±0.76
5	68.5±0.66	76.2±0.26	66.3±0.74	67.2±0.45
6	82.9±0.29	87.4±0.49	79.1±0.63	78.2±0.34

Figure: drug release profiles of formulations ACFNX1 to ACFCN2.

Table: drug release profile of formulation ACFCNG1 to ACFCNGX.

Time in (hours)	ACFCNG1	ACFCNG2	ACFCNX	ACFCNGX
0	0	0	0	0
1	11.5±0.91	12.9±0.16	21.3±0.23	29.1±0.34
2	23.4±0.73	26.5±0.84	32.9±0.34	37.1±0.62
3	42.5±0.59	45.8±0.53	39.2±0.46	44.1±0.58
4	52.5±0.52	55.3±0.72	47.5±0.69	54.9±0.37
5	61.9±0.69	64.1±0.11	55.2±0.47	60.4±0.93
6	69.5±0.28	75.6±32	71.8±0.39	70.2±0.11
7	74.9±0.24	83.5±0.22	82.1±0.72	-
8	86.52±38	94.4±0.82	-	-

Figure: drug release profiles of formulations ACFCNG1 to ACFCNGX.

Cumulative Drug Release % And Sustained Release Duration Of Formulations:

Formulation name	%cumulative drug release value	Sustained release duration(in hours)
ACFN1	71.2%±0.23	6
ACFX2	61.5%±0.92	6
ACFG1	71.1%±0.95	6
ACFNG1	82.1%±0.24	6
ACFNGX	81%±0.37	5
ACFNX2	87.4%±0.44	6
ACFCN2	78.2%±0.39	6
ACFCNG2	94.4%±0.71	8
ACFCNX	82.1%±0.84	7
ACFCNGX	70.2%±0.34	6

Table: %drug release of pure drug and optimized gel formulation.

TIME (min)	Pure Drug	Formulation
0	5.21±0.85	0
30	38.4±0.23	5.9±0.19
45	72.9±0.32	11.7±0.45
60	95.4±0.41	18.6±0.53
90		26.7±0.36
120		38.5±0.26
180		68.7±0.61
240		84.3±0.58
300		94.9±0.10

Figure: %drug release of pure drug and optimized gel formulation.

Viscosity:

The above selected formulations are subjected to viscosity and determination. In contrast to pure drug suspension which shows the drug release within 1 hour other gel formulations exhibited sustained drug release ranging from 5 to 8 hours respectively. Among all formulations ACFCNG2 showed sustained release of 94.3% up to 8 hours.

Table: viscosity at different speeds:

Formulation code	Viscosity (in cps) at different speed (rpm)				
	10rpm	20 rpm	30 rpm	40 rpm	50 rpm
ACF6	29	17	13	9	6
ACFN1	91	72	56	38	27
ACFX2	97	76	61	43	29
ACFG1	120	82	67	52	48
ACFNG1	259	217	163	115	79
ACFNGX	247	206	157	134	94
ACFNX2	237	192	167	131	89
ACFCN2	219	176	129	98	78
ACFCNG2	340	285	227	179	145
ACFNX	207	188	141	109	87
ACFNGX	215	169	155	130	95

Figure: viscosity of selected formulation.

Cubosome dispersion (ACF6) showed less viscosity as expected due to absence of gelling agent. However other formulations showed considerable range of viscosity due to presence of gelling agents. Among all the formulation, those containing carbopol 934 B.P showed higher range of viscosity due to its thickening swelling capability.

pH:**Table: Ph of various formulations.**

Formulation name	pH
ACF6	6.82
ACFN1	6.78
ACFX2	6.65
ACFG1	6.6
ACFNG1	6.51
ACFNGX	6.85
ACFNX2	6.69
ACFCN2	6.62
ACFCNG2	6.38
ACFCNX1	6.54
ACFCNGX	6.58

Figure: pH of selected gel formulations.

Microscopy:

The cubosome dispersion and floating gels are observed under microscopically. The ordinary cubosome dispersion contains individual entities, where as in case of gel formulation the gelling agents used forms like a matrix like structure around cubosome units that acts as a medium of gastro retention by forming floating gels and prolonging drug release.

Figure: Floating Gels Are Observed Under Microscopically.

Kinetics of drug release:

Based on the drug release values of gel formulation (ACFCNG2) are studies for release kinetics; inferences are drawn from below values:

Table: kinetics of drug release:

Time(Hrs)	Cumulative % Drug Release	% Drug Remaining	Square Root Time	Log Cumulative % Remaining	Log Time	Log Cumulative % Drug Released	% Drug Released	Cube Root Of % Drug Remaining (Wt)	Wo- Wt
0	0	100	0	2	0	0	100	4.642	0
1	12.9	87.1	1	1.94	0	1.111	12.9	4.433	0.209
2	26.5	73.1	1.414	1.866	0.301	1.423	13.6	4.189	0.453
3	45.8	54.2	1.732	1.734	0.477	1.661	19.3	3.784	0.858
4	55.3	44.7	2	1.65	0.602	1.743	9.5	3.549	1.293
5	64.1	35.9	2.236	1.555	0.699	1.807	8.8	3.299	1.343
6	75.6	24.4	2.449	1.387	0.778	1.879	11.5	2.9	1.742
7	83.5	16.5	2.646	1.217	0.845	1.922	7.9	2.546	2.096
8	94.4	5.6	2.828	0.748	0.903	1.975	10.9	1.776	2.866

Figure: drug release from optimized cubosome gel formulation.

Figure: drug release from optimized cubosome gel formulation.

Table: Results of standard deviation kinetic models:

KINETIC MODEL	r ² values
ZERO ORDER	0.988
FIRST ORDER	0.982
KORSMAEYER-PEPPAS	0.973
HICKSON CROWEL	0.933
HIGUCHI	0.931

Based on the above results it is inferred that cubosomes gel formulation (ACFCNG2) follows zero order kinetics with anomalous/non-fickian diffusion (swellable and cylindrical matrix).

STABILITY STUDIES:

pH:

Table: pH of optimized formulation ACF6.

Time in Days	pH of ACFCNG2
0	6.52
30	6.32
60	6.3
90	6.2

Figure: pH of optimized formulation AC.

Viscosity:

Table: Viscosity of optimized Formulation ACF6:

Time in days	10rpm	20rpm	30rpm	40rpm	50rpm
1	340	285	227	179	145
30	339	284	226	177	144
60	339	283	224	177	143
90	339	283	224	176	143

Figure: viscosity of optimized formulation ACF6.

Table 8.15 stability studies of optimized formulation ACFCNG2.

%drug release	Time in days			
	1	30	60	90
ACFCNG2	94.4±0.63	93.9±0.49	93.1±0.29	92.7±0.40

Minor changes in parameters are observed conforming the stability of selected optimized formulations.

CONCLUSION

Cubosomes can be formed by simple combination of biologically compatible lipids (GMO) and water and are thus well suited for pharmaceutical and body tissue. The stability to form Cubosomes during manufacture offers enhanced flexibility for product development efforts. The above research specifies cubosomal utility as controlled release drug carrier. Prolonged Gastro retention is achieved when they are formulated as floating gels maintaining the cubosome structure. Although they possess advantageous characteristics, there is a still long Way to go before their clinical application. In near future we hope that a way will be opened for such formulations to be used as novel drug delivery systems to circumvent the drawbacks of conventional dosage forms.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

It is proud to express my heartfelt to gratitude to my beloved institutional guide. Centre for pharmaceutical science, IST and JNTUH for their voluble guidance, cooperation, affectionate encourage and moral support throughout the course of this investigation.

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